

THE ACTIVITY STRUCTURE OF THE COMPONENT THAT TRANSMITS EXPERIENCE IN THE TRAINING SYSTEM

Ibrahimov F.N.

*Head of the Department of Natural Sciences and their Teaching Technology
of the Sheki branch of the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University,*

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0775-1048>

Jabraylova N.B.

*Department of Natural Sciences and
their teaching technology of Sheki branch of ADPU,
head teacher*

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3490-6201>

Abstract

The article first explains the concept of "activity of the experience-transmitting component" in the training system. The organization and management of the learning activity of the receiving party-students is an important element of the activity of the sending party-teacher, which can be called a "teaching activity" if we allow a little approximation.

The authors of the article distinguish between genetic-structural and functional-structural model of teaching activity. Thanks to the generalization of research materials, the genetic-structural model: a) to set the main and special tasks for the student and to ensure that the student perceives it as a perceived goal; b) provide students with the necessary training information; c) study of learning materials, assignments to train skills and habits, and d) managerial activity: it is concluded that students include activities such as organizing, monitoring, evaluating, analyzing work. It is stated that the functional model includes three stages (introductory-motivational stage, operational-cognitive stage, control-evaluation stage), which

Keywords: Experience transfer activity; activity structure; structural elements; genetic-structural model; functional-structural model; introduction-motivation stage; operational cognitive phase; control-evaluation stage.

Relevance of the research topic. The essence of the learning process can be interpreted in the scheme of "experience-learning material-experience", in other words, the process can be considered as a system that includes interconnected parts and has some properties that are not always in separate parts. When we move away from the nature of the elements of the system and focus on the relationship between them, we are confronted with the concept of the structure of the system. The dialectical unity of the structure with the elements is the main feature of the system. The essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, ie the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, the specificity of the relationship of the object to the situation. It is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary connections here without studying the elements that make up the system and their interaction. It should not be forgotten that there are certain interdependencies between systems, including one another and dialectical connections. Based on SASHaporinski's idea that "large systems" include "small systems", the teacher's and learner's activities and learning material in the learning process can also be considered as "small systems" included in the process. The solution to the everlasting problems of the learning process can be approached despite what we have said. Determining the structure (genetic and functional) of these "subsystems" leads to approaches to improving the management of the training system. However, no systematic research has been conducted in this direction, which, naturally speaking, is the "place"

of the idea of systematic analysis of L. Bertalanfi by academician A.X.Mirzajanzade.

Interpretation of research materials. One of the scientific sources known to us has the following opinion: "Looking at the psychopedagogical pages of the past centuries, we see that in the history of world education, a rich experience has been accumulated at the root of the transfer of knowledge to the student. The ideas put forward and applied to implement the process of knowledge transfer to the student can be grouped into three groups: 1) Enlightening learning ideas; 2) Developmental learning ideas; 3) Educational learning ideas "[2; 9]. Another pedagogical literature emphasizes: "Sometimes it is thought that learning is a simple process of imparting knowledge to students. In fact, it is the core of education. Training has complex functions. There are two sides to the training as a teacher-student interaction: teaching and learning. The effectiveness of training depends to a large extent on the proper interaction of teachers and students in the teaching process, the level of cognitive activity of students, their interest in learning "[1; 210]. We can continue to think about training, because there are too many opinions about it in scientific sources. Based on the generalization of our research materials, we believe that training in educational institutions is a way of implementing education, education, upbringing and cognitive development should be understood as the main tasks of the learning process, and the learning process can be more accurately interpreted through the concept of "system". In our opinion, Training in modern times should be understood as a system of

education adequate to the emerging educational space in accordance with the challenges of the IV industrial revolution. The main components of this system are the educator and the learner.

The problem of transforming the learning process into a well-managed system is everlasting. This is due to the pedagogical nature of the training. If we approach training as a cybernetic model of management, we have to express our interpretations in a different context. As it is known, E.A.Klimov has formed the following four important features of a good management system: a) clarity, clarity of the purpose of management; b) timely feedback; c) the relationships are of a consistent operational nature; d) accuracy of information on each subsequent condition of the controlled object. It should be noted that the adoption of a cybernetic model of management in the learning process is based on its abstraction, allowing it to be viewed as a process independent of content. Therefore, E.A.Klimov considers this process as a complex management

system. Academician AI Berg writes that it is quite clear that training can be considered as a management system. The most important and specific feature here is that the object of management in this system is the person himself. In this system, the object of management is not only the student as an individual, but also the student's activities aimed at acquiring and developing knowledge. There are two governing bodies, which to some extent regulate their activities. E.A.Klimov interpreted this as follows (scheme 1) [3; 230-238] It is also an activity aimed at the acquisition and development of students' knowledge. There are two governing bodies, which to some extent regulate their activities. E.A.Klimov interpreted this as follows (scheme 1) [3; 230-238] It is also an activity aimed at the acquisition and development of students' knowledge. There are two governing bodies, which to some extent regulate their activities. E.A.Klimov interpreted this as follows (scheme 1) [3; 230-238]

External feedback Scheme 1

Naturally, the level of effective training and the development of its theoretical foundations is determined by the level of development of pedagogical thought of each generation, and this process is constantly improving. In our opinion, the system of education formed in accordance with the current level of development of pedagogical thought and pedagogical practice (or rather, the level at which we understand this treasure) should include: adequacy to the emerging educational space in accordance with the challenges of the IV industrial revolution; constructivism that will lead to the development of students' thinking; cooperative learning that will lead to their social development; creation of conditions for independent acquisition of knowledge; independent acquisition of knowledge and skills; activity of the teacher based on the principles of acting as an organizing coordinator, in some cases as an arbitrator ;, problem, algorithmic, programming, differentiation, etc. approaches to transform themselves as subsystems, to move with the "opportunity-action-new quality" paradigm.

It is worth noting that the concept of "student learning activities" has emerged in educational psychology. Successes in the field of the concept of activity have allowed us to approach this issue from a new perspective, and the concept of "teaching activity" has emerged in pedagogical psychology. Although training is an important characteristic of educational

activity, it does not cover all aspects of it. Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. Assimilation and teaching activities are essentially different events. Assimilation is an integral part not only in the learning process, but in every field of activity. Educational activity is a type of activity, a unique form of social activity of the individual. The concept of educational activity (D.V.Elkonin, V.V.Davidov, etc.) distinguishes the following components in the structure of educational activity: 1) teaching situation (or tasks); 2) educational operations; 3) control; 4) price.

The learner in the system of education is the pupil, the student, the participant and others - "someone who intends to master the necessary part of human experience", and the teacher is the "carrier", the subject of transferring human experience in accordance with the level of development of civilization.

It is rightly emphasized in the scientific literature that the structure of the training system includes cognitive needs, learning motives, learning goals, objectives, learning activities [4; 131]. It should be noted here that, regardless of the level of perception of the activity, the perception of the goal always remains a necessary feature of it. In the absence of this sign, human activity, especially learning activity, cannot exist. The goal is a "system-building component", a "motion model" [6; 172]. "In the structure of learning and teaching, which is included in the training system,

there are components that are internally interconnected" [12; 178].

In our opinion, the first element in the structure of the teacher's activity, which is the subject of teaching, should be considered preparatory work. In many cases, we are talking about an important element of the teacher's activity - the management of students' learning activities. However, the teacher's activity should not be limited to organizational leadership. After all, it is necessary to provide appropriate information about the training material, and for this it is necessary to prepare this information, select visual and technical means of training, and so on. Various educational activities, work with parents, etc. are included in the daily activities of the teacher. includes.

N.M.Kazimov and A.Sh.Hashimov characterize the teacher's activity in the training as follows: to organize the activity of the teacher in the system of activity, ie all aspects related to the organization and management of the student's cognitive activity, the activity aimed at the education and development of the student; to motivate the student to be active; to monitor student activities; to direct student activities; to analyze and summarize the results of student activities, etc. includes [7; 108-111].

By the way, the activity of a teacher is often called teaching, and this term does not fully reflect the multifaceted activity of the teacher. After all, teaching is usually associated with the transfer of knowledge and information to students, which is only part of the teacher's activity. It would also be incorrect to call the teacher's activity management of the learning process, which includes another part of the teacher's activity [4; 131].

In order to share experiences, the activities of the presenter-teacher are concentrated in the integration of teaching and learning activities in the learning process [11; 306-307]. Before the process, it manifests itself in the form of preparation.

The activity of the teacher in the process of training consists of the following stages of preparation for the teaching activity:

1. Preparation for the school year (study of the training program, development of a schedule or calendar plan, planning of work with parents, extracurricular educational work, etc.).

2. Preparation for the study of the next content: scientific, logical, methodological, historical, etc. of the training material. aspect analysis, determination of minimum (necessary) knowledge, skills and habits to be acquired by students, development of a system of specific and general teaching skills for the subject, construction of a model of student learning activities on a given topic, determination of interdisciplinary and interdisciplinary links, class to be given to students and identify the range of knowledge, skills and habits (previously acquired) necessary for extracurricular activities and choose ways to update them, etc.

3. We are ready to conduct the next lesson (or other form of organization): analysis of the results of the previous training and preparation of the plan for the given (upcoming) training, selection of teaching aids,

preparation of technical means, obtaining other training equipment, etc. [8; 334-350].

The second element of the transmitter's activity is the organization and guidance of students' learning activities, which can be called teaching activities (based on feedback).

The model of formation and development of the implementation of the learning process (genetic) consists of the following types of work: b) to provide students with the necessary training information using various teaching aids and techniques; c) give assignments to study the training material, to train skills and habits; d) managerial activity: organization of students' learning activities, control, assessment, work analysis [9; 571].

The functional model of the teacher's implementation of the process of teaching the topic consists of three stages, which corresponds to the stage of the functional model of the student's learning activity:

1. *Introduction-motivation stage.* At this stage, the teacher carries out the following work:

- a) creation of the main problem situation in order to clarify the place, role and importance of the subject in the system of teaching (why this subject should be studied); "Here, the teacher must keep in mind that the novelty of knowledge, problem-solving, the use of scientific and technical innovations, the importance of knowledge for the individual, for society, the involvement of children in creative activities, and so on. are tools that help to increase the cognitive interest of the learner in the learning process" [5; 284-285]; b) formulation of educational goals and objectives facing students; c) clarifying the plan for acquiring the minimum of knowledge, skills and habits to be acquired;

2. *Operation - cognitive stage.* At this stage, the teacher carries out the following types of work: a) teaching - providing students with the necessary information by various methods using visual and teaching aids; b) organization and management of students' educational work (involvement of students in educational-cognitive activities, organization of control-assessment activities); c) ongoing monitoring and evaluation of students' learning.

It should be noted that during the training, the teacher always pays attention to how the students work, what they have achieved, what they have difficulties in, whether they have made mistakes. The teacher cannot successfully take the next methodological step without monitoring how the teaching material is mastered by the students. Emphasizing the importance of this, one of the authors NMKazimov writes that the teacher monitors the activities of students in different ways, determines that the task, the question is clearly understood by all students. The progress of the task is monitored, who is attentive, test questions are asked to students, exercises are organized to work independently if necessary, short conversations are held with individual students if necessary, and so on. [7; 108-111].

Current monitoring allows students to see the strengths as well as the shortcomings that are typical of

teaching. Students' attention is drawn to those successes or shortcomings, shortcomings are not allowed to accumulate, they are eliminated in time [3; 230-238].

Current supervision has ample opportunities for improving the teacher, increasing his pedagogical skills, and, as a result, raising the level of educational work.

3. *Control - evaluation stage.* At this stage, the teacher carries out the following work: a) generalization of the studied material of the studied topic in different forms; b) organizing and directing students' learning activities to generalize the learning material; c) evaluation and final control of each student's learning work on the implementation of the subject study plan; d) to clarify the shortcomings and mistakes of individual students in the implementation of the plan for the study of the topic and to organize work to eliminate them.

In connection with the latter, N.M.Kazimov shows that in the process of training, the teaching of each subject is summed up. The state of students' mastery of the topic can be analyzed after one lesson or several lessons. Analyzing the results of the student's teaching activities, the teacher identifies the shortcomings, deficiencies and takes measures to eliminate them. The reasons can be many: the quality of the teacher's teaching activities, the degree of attention of students in the classroom, their attitude to learning, the state of conversations, the degree of business, the ability to work independently, and so on. [7; 108-111]

One of the main elements of a teacher's activity is related to extracurricular activities. These can be divided into two areas: a) extracurricular activities related to the teaching of the subject; b) extracurricular activities related to educational work.

By the way, it should be noted that the following traditional classification of a teacher's creative work is widely noted in the pedagogical literature: 1) constructive activity of a teacher; 2) organizational activity of the teacher; 3) teacher's communicative activity; 4) gnostic activity of the teacher [11; 306-307].

The teacher's activity model for the implementation of the learning process (genetic and functional) has a key role, both practical and theoretical, in terms of identifying and systematizing teaching methods. The compatibility of the teacher's activity model with the student's activity model involves the coordination of teaching and learning methods, which is related to the essence of the learning process.

The structure of any activity differs both in the content of motives and the specificity of other elements [12; 178-179]. The diversity of structural elements and functional dependence of the goal-oriented and regulated activities of teachers and students in the learning process give rise to the diversity of the material nomenclature, as well as the need to create a system [10; 446]. Not content with what is said about the model of the teacher component in such a system, its functions, personal qualities, we turn our attention to the very interesting and our We would like to complete with a reasonable consideration.

There are two epigraphs in the title: "A swimming teacher is needed" (Announcement in a French provincial newspaper) and "They want to teach today what happened only yesterday...".

The author of the newspaper ad in the first epigraph ("Swimming teacher required") had no doubt that a swimming teacher could teach a child to swim, that is, he knew that a teacher could teach him to swim. The doubt here was how the teacher himself was. Can he do what he teaches? The owner of the ad may set a number of other requirements for the swimming teacher, such as the ability to rescue a drowning person, the ability to give artificial respiration to the victim, the knowledge of the anatomy and physiology of the feet and hands, and so on.

There is nothing so surprising here. Thus, a teacher must have more knowledge, skills and habits than he / she teaches in matters related to his / her professional training.

In connection with the second epigraph, the author of the book narrates an interesting episode in the person of an American. The Czech language teacher willingly agrees with the young American, who does not know a word, to the author of an advertisement. In return, he hires a teacher for half of the amount he will receive. The day before, he goes to his teacher as a student and the next day, as a teacher, he begins to teach others as a teacher.

Here, too, the point is clear: the teacher must know what he will teach in today's lesson, as well as the material after each lesson.

A common conclusion from both epigraphs is that the teacher must have more knowledge of the material he is going to teach, and he must have it long before he teaches it.

Here is an important aspect of the pedagogical problem: how to assess the resulting "many" and "before" requirements, and most importantly: what is the "pedagogical dimension"?

When it comes to our topic, a number of issues arise: one of them is that in order to assess students' analytical and heuristic skills (mental activity skills) in the learning process, the teacher must have a higher level of these skills. In order to form an analytical and heuristic way of thinking in students, the teacher must have a deep knowledge of related science in the field of his subject, as well as a conscious understanding of the essence of this process more and earlier than the student, and purposeful pedagogical skills. For this purpose, it is necessary to touch upon the problem of "knowledge" in pedagogy, to understand the essence of the concepts of "heuristics" and "algorithm" in modern science, to understand their pedagogical aspects [8; 334-350].

Scientific novelty of research work. Models of activity (genetic and functional) for the implementation of the teacher's learning process have been identified, which have a key role in both practical and theoretical terms in terms of identifying and systematizing teaching methods. The compatibility of the teacher's model of activity with the student's model of activity presupposes a combination of teaching and learning

methods. This is due to the essence of the training process.

Theoretical significance of the research. The identification of models of activity (genetic and functional) for the implementation of the teacher's learning process has a positive impact on the development of the theory of improving the management of the system.

Practical significance of the research. The identification of models of teacher activity (genetic and functional) for the implementation of the learning process creates an adequate environment for the elimination of errors that may be manifested in the activities of practical educators in the direct (indirect) management of this system.

The result. 1) Models of activity of the teacher on the implementation of the learning process (genetic and functional) have both a practical and theoretical key role in terms of choosing and systematizing the forms of mental activity. 2) The operating models of the main components of the training system are compatible. This is due to the essence of the training process.

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UDC 377.8

ON THE QUALITY OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF TEACHING STAFF IN THE SYSTEM OF TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION IN A NEW PERSPECTIVE

Shalgynbaeva K.K.

Doctor of Pedagogy, Professor of the Department of Social Pedagogy and Self-Knowledge of the L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan.

Mutaliev A.S.

Candidate of Pedagogy, Senior Lecturer of the Department of Social Pedagogy and self-knowledge of the L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan.

Slambekov Y.T.

Doctoral student of the Department of Social Pedagogy and Self-Knowledge of the L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan.

УДК 377.8

О КАЧЕСТВЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КАДРОВ В СИСТЕМЕ ТЕХНИЧЕСКОГО И ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В НОВОЙ ПЕРСПЕКТИВЕ

Шалгынбаева К.К.

доктор педагогических наук, профессор кафедры социальной педагогики и самопознания Евразийского национального университета имени Л.Н.Гумилева, Нур-Султан, Казахстан.

Муталиева А.Ш.

кандидат педагогических наук, старший преподаватель кафедры социальная педагогика и самопознания Евразийского национального университета имени Л.Н.Гумилева, Нур-Султан, Казахстан.

Слаббеков Е.Т.

докторант кафедры социальной педагогики и самопознания Евразийского национального университета имени Л.Н.Гумилева, Нур-Султан, Казахстан.

Abstract

The article examines the assessment of the quality of professional trainings, which are aimed at training the pedagogical specialists, graduates of technical and vocational education that are described in the theoretical works